

MODELING OF VOID FORMATION DURING RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING

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SUMMARY: The void content within RTM parts is responsible for a severe degradation of part strength. Due to the non-uniform permeability of the preform on sub-tow scales, formation of air void highly depends on the resin velocity and the surface tension at the flow front during mold filling. Capillary number is the decisive factor affecting the void formation. In this study, a mathematical model for the void formation as a function of capillary number was developed. Experiment was performed for a one-dimensional flow in which the capillary number varies with the moving flow front. The proposed model could efficiently predict the size and content of air voids. Applied to a body panel of a passenger car, the potential of this model to predict the void distribution in arbitrary shapes is illustrated.

KEYWORDS: RTM, Voids, Permeability, Capillary Pressure, Mold Filling, Microscopic Flow

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced composites generally experience a degradation of strength and modulus with increasing void content [1~7]. In the manufacturing process of RTM, the formation of air voids highly depends on the resin velocity at the flow front and the surface tension of resin during mold filling. Since the microscopic architecture of the fiber preform is non-uniform, the local permeability of the fiber preform as well as the capillary pressure differ by orders of magnitude between inside the fiber tows and the outside. As a result, resin velocity varies dramatically from point to point. This non-uniform flow leads to the formation of numerous air voids on a microscopic scale [8~11]. The void content mainly depends on the capillary number of the resin flow during mold filling, which is defined as the ratio of viscous force to capillary force [12~14].

In this study, a mathematical model was developed to describe the microscopic resin flow and void formation at the flow front of resin. Experiments were performed for a porous flow through a long strip of fiber preform. The cross section of the molded part was scanned to measure the void size and content. A good agreement was found between the model prediction and the experimental result. This model was incorporated into a numerical simulation program for the mold filling analysis of RTM to calculate the distribution of void content at different locations. The developed model and the code can be used to determine the optimal processing conditions to minimize the void content within RTM parts.

VOID MODEL

The preform used in RTM consists of fiber tows with regular or random textures. Between

the tows are the pores or channels, through which the resin can flow with less viscous resistance. The local permeability of the preform is much lower within the tows, because the gap size between fiber filaments is much smaller than between fiber tows. On the other hand, the capillary pressure is larger within the tow. With high velocities of the resin front, voids are formed within the fiber tows because the resin moves faster in the channels, Figure 1a. For low velocities, the capillary flow within the tow dominates and the voids are formed within the channel, Figure 1b.

Figure 1. Void formation within and between the tows

Assuming the channel as a straight two-dimensional cavity with an equivalent gap clearance, the resin velocity in the channel between two tows can be approximated as

$$u_c = -F_{K,C}(\phi) \frac{d_c^2}{\mu} \frac{dP}{dn} \quad (1)$$

where u_c is the resin velocity, $F_{K,C}(\phi)$ is the shape factors for the channel flow, ϕ is the porosity, d_c is the average gap size between the two adjacent fiber tows and μ is the resin viscosity (see Figure 2). Subscript C stands for 'channel' and subscript K denotes the local permeability. n is the coordinate normal to the flow front. In order to simplify the problem, the upper and lower boundaries of the tow is assumed impermeable while the left and right boundaries are open. The shape factor $F_{K,C}(\phi)$ is to compensate the difference between the actual configuration and the straight channel approximation. It is also assumed that the capillary pressure within the channel is negligible.

Figure 2. Resin flow in the channel between fiber tows

Since $\Delta t_{l_T,C}$ is small compared to the total mold filling time, the global pressure gradient is assumed to remain constant during $\Delta t_{l_T,C}$. The time $\Delta t_{l_T,C}$ required for the flow front to move the cross sectional width of the tow l_T can be approximated as

$$\Delta t_{l_T,C} \approx - \frac{\mu l_T}{F_{K,C}(\phi) d_c^2} \frac{dP}{dn} \quad (2)$$

The capillary pressure within the tow is approximated by incorporating $F_{c,T}(\phi)$ as a shape

factor

$$P_{c,T} = \frac{F_{c,T}(\phi)\gamma \cos \theta}{d_T} \quad (3)$$

where d_T is the average distance between fibers (see Figure 3), γ is the surface tension of resin and θ is the contact angle.

Figure 3. Flow within tows of non-homogeneous porous material

The porous flow within the tow is also approximated using a shape factor related to the permeability of the tow. Defining l as the impregnation distance between the leading edge of the tow and the flow front, the resin velocity is given as

$$u_T = \frac{dl}{dt} = F_{K,T}(\phi) \frac{d_T^2}{\mu} \left(-\frac{dP}{dn} + \frac{P_{c,T}}{l} \right) \quad (4)$$

where subscript T denotes ‘tow’, subscript c stands for ‘capillary’ and $F_{K,T}(\phi)$ is the shape factor for the tow permeability.

Integrating Eq. 4 with respect to the time yields

$$\Delta t_{l,T} = \frac{1}{F_{K,T}(\phi) \frac{d_T^2}{\mu}} \left\{ l_T - \frac{P_{c,T}}{dP/dn} \log \left(1 + \frac{dP/dn}{P_{c,T}} l_T \right) \right\} \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta t_{l,T}$ is the time required for the resin front to travel the distance l_T within the tow.

Dividing Eq. 5 by Eq. 2, the ratio of times $\Delta t_{l,T}$ and $\Delta t_{l,C}$ is given by

$$\frac{\Delta t_{l,T}}{\Delta t_{l,C}} = \frac{F_{K,C}(\phi) d_C^2}{F_{K,T}(\phi) d_T^2} \left\{ 1 - \frac{P_{c,T}/l_T}{dP/dn} \log \left(1 + \frac{dP/dn}{P_{c,T}/l_T} \right) \right\} \quad (6)$$

The ratio of the viscous force to the capillary force is defined as the capillary number [13].

$$Ca = \frac{\mu v}{\gamma} \quad (7)$$

where v is the average velocity based on the flow rate per unit area and γ is the surface tension. A modified capillary number was suggested to account for the effect of contact angle θ between fiber and resin [14].

$$Ca^* = \frac{\mu v}{\gamma \cos \theta} \quad (8)$$

Darcy’s law can be used to describe the average resin velocity normal to the flow front.

$$v = -\frac{K(\phi) dP}{\mu dn} \quad (9)$$

where $K(\phi)$ is the permeability of the fiber preform as a function of porosity. Inserting Eqs. 3, 8 and 9 into Eq. 6, the time ratio can be expressed as a function of the capillary number as follows.

$$\frac{\Delta t_{l_r,T}}{\Delta t_{l_r,C}} = \frac{F_{K,C}(\phi)d_C^2}{F_{K,T}(\phi)d_T^2} \left\{ 1 - \frac{K(\phi)F_{c,T}(\phi)}{Ca^*d_T l_T} \log \left(1 + \frac{Ca^*d_T l_T}{K(\phi)F_{c,T}(\phi)} \right) \right\} \quad (10)$$

This time ratio describes the competition of the flow front velocity within and between the tows. It is assumed that the void size and content is determined by this time ratio. $F_{K,C}(\phi)$, $F_{K,T}(\phi)$, $F_{c,T}(\phi)$, $K(\phi)$, d_T and l_T are properties of the fiber preform, not the resin or the pressure distribution. Therefore, for a given fiber preform, the time ratio depends on the capillary number only, which gives a good reason for the previous experiments by Chen et al. [13]. Rohatgi et al. [14] also reported the dependence of the void content on the capillary number for various fluids and process conditions.

Size of the Air Voids

The formation of air void is classified into four categories according to the time ratio defined in Eq. 10.

$$\text{Case 1: } \frac{\Delta t_{l_r,T}}{\Delta t_{l_r,C}} \gg 1$$

For high capillary numbers, the flow front moves faster in channels and the voids form within the tows. l_r is the distance that the flow front moves within the tow during the time $\Delta t_{l_r,C}$ which is determined iteratively by Eq. 5. The cross sectional width of the void, l_v is given as follows, Figure 4.

$$l_v = l_T - l_r \quad (11)$$

The aspect ratio of the void $\frac{h_v}{l_v}$ should be determined experimentally.

Figure 4. Size of the void within a fiber tow

$$\text{Case 2: } \frac{\Delta t_{l_r,T}}{\Delta t_{l_r,C}} \approx 1$$

The flow front velocities within channels and tows compete with each other, so the air voids do not form on either side.

$$l_v = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Case 3: } \frac{\Delta t_{l_r,T}}{\Delta t_{l_r,C}} \ll 1$$

From Eq. 2, the distance l_C that the resin front moves during the time $\Delta t_{l_r,T}$ is given as

$$l_c = -F_{k,c}(\phi) \frac{d_c^2}{\mu} \frac{dP}{dn} \Delta t_{l,T} \quad (13)$$

The cross sectional width of the void l_v can be obtained as follows, Figure 5.

$$l_v = l_T - l_c \quad (14)$$

The average aspect ratio of the void $\frac{h_v}{l_v}$ is to be determined experimentally.

Figure 5. Size of the void within the channel

Case 4: Maximum void size

In some experiments, it has been observed that there exists a maximum void size for a give fiber volume fraction. In such a case, the maximum void size should be measured experimentally to be used as a threshold value in this model.

Number of Voids

The maximum number of the voids per unit volume is determined by the microscopic architecture of the fiber preform, which is roughly the same as the number of tows or channels in which voids can form. This maximum number is determined by counting the number of tows or channels in the microscopic images of the cross sections. In this model,

the number of voids per unit volume is related to the time ratio $\frac{\Delta t_{l,T}}{\Delta t_{l,C}}$ as follows.

$$N_{v,C} = \Pi_C(\phi) \left(\frac{\Delta t_{l,C}}{\Delta t_{l,T}} - 1 \right) N_C, \quad \frac{\Delta t_{l,T}}{\Delta t_{l,C}} < 1 \quad (16)$$

$$N_{v,T} = \Pi_T(\phi) \left(\frac{\Delta t_{l,T}}{\Delta t_{l,C}} - 1 \right) N_T, \quad \frac{\Delta t_{l,T}}{\Delta t_{l,C}} > 1 \quad (17)$$

Here, N_C and N_T are the numbers of channels and tows per unit cross sectional area. $N_{v,C}$ and $N_{v,T}$ are the actual numbers of voids per unit area within channels and tows, respectively. $\Pi_C(\phi)$ and $\Pi_T(\phi)$ are the probability factors of void formation for channels and tows. It is observed from experiments that the number of voids per unit cross sectional area is also limited. In such a case, the threshold value for the number of voids per area should be determined experimentally.

EXPERIMENTS

Experiments were performed to characterize the formation of voids with varying flow front

velocity. Vinylester resin (Aerotran 50437-8, Ashland Chemical) with MEKP (Lupersol DDM-9, Pennwalt Chemical) of 1.5% by weight was injected through random chopped glass fabric (CM450-723, Owens Corning). The preform was 250mm long, 30mm wide and 3mm thick. The viscosity of resin was 0.175 Pa·s and the surface tension of resin was 29mN/m at the room temperature of 26.8°C. The average diameter of the fiber filament was 13 μ m. The average cross sectional tow width l_T was 7.2 $\times 10^{-4}$ m. The injection was performed at 150kPa using compressed nitrogen. The preform was made by stacking 3 plies of random glass fabric, and the fiber volume fraction was 19.2%. Since the experiment was done in less than two minutes, the viscosity and the surface tension were assumed constant. The cross section of the cured specimen was scanned at different locations using a microscope as shown in Figure 6. Due to the limited resolution of the microscope used in this study, the inspection of the tow voids was not conducted.

Figure 6. Void formation at different distances from the injection gate

The shape factors are determined by curve fitting the experimental data. According to Eq. 9, the pressure gradient and hence the resin velocity and the capillary number is inversely proportional to the distance between the inlet and the flow front. The comparison between the results from the experiment and the model is shown in Figure 7 as functions of the distance from the inlet.

(a) Number of voids within the area of 0.84 \times 3(mm²) (b) Average width of voids

(c) Volumetric void content

Figure 7. Void size and content measured at different locations from the injection gate

Table 1. Model constants obtained by curve fitting the measured void content and size

Model Constant	Curve Fit Value
$F_{K,C}$	0.2785
$F_{c,T}$	22.5
$F_{K,T}$	8.4348
N_C	5.159 (per mm^2)
Maximum $N_{v,C}$	2.540 (per mm^2) (averaged after 0.08m)
Maximum l_v	0.34mm
Π_C	0.8323

NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

The proposed model was incorporated into an RTM simulation program (developed in Seoul National University, Korea) to calculate the distribution of the void content. A numerical example for the mold filling of the hood panel of a passenger car is shown in Figure 8. The considered part consists of a skin panel and a stiffener. A rigid foam core, which is assumed to be impermeable, is inserted between the skin panel and the stiffener. Injection was performed at 8.0×10^5 Pa. The total mold filling time was 362.4s. Figure 8c and 8d shows the predicted distribution of void content within the channels and the tows, respectively.

CONCLUSION

A mathematical model was developed to analyze the void formation during RTM process. The developed model can predict the size and content of air voids within and between the fiber tows as functions of the capillary number. Experiments were performed for one-dimensional RTM process in which the capillary number varies with the moving flow front. The proposed model could accurately predict the void formation at different locations and can be used to determine the optimal process conditions during the mold filling process.

REFERENCES

1. Greszczuk, L.B., "Effect of Voids on Strength Properties of Filamentary Composites, *Proceedings of 22nd Annual Meeting of the Reinforced Plastics Division of The Society of the Plastics Industry*, pp 20.A-1 to 20.A.10, 1967
2. Hancox, N.L., "The Effect of Flaws and Voids on the Shear Properties of CFRP", *J. Mater. Sci.*, 12, 884-892, 1977
3. Judd, N.C.W. and W.W. Wright, "Voids and Their Effects on the Mechanical Properties of Composites - An Appraisal", *SAMPE Journal*, 14, 10-14, January/February, 1978
4. Yosida, H.T., T. Ogasa and R. Hayashi, "Statistical Approach to the Relationship between ILSS and Void Content of CFRP", *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, 25, 3-18, 1986
5. Harper, B.D., G.H. Staab and R.S. Chen, "A Note on the Effects of Voids Upon the Hygral and Mechanical Properties of AS4/3502 Graphite/Epoxy", *J. of Composite Materials*, Vol. 21, 281-289, 1987
6. Feldgoise, S., M.F. Foley, D. Martin, and J. Bohan, "The Effect of Microvoid Content on Composite Shear Strength", *23rd International SAMPE Technical Conference*, 1991
7. K.J. Bowles and S. Frimpong, "Void Effects on the Interlaminar Shear Strength of Unidirectional Graphite-Fiber-Reinforced Composites", *J. of Composite Materials*, Vol. 26, No. 10, 1487-1509, 1992
8. "Mold Filling in Resin Transfer Molding", *SAMPE Quarterly*, 53, 1991
9. Patel, N., V. Rohatgi and L.J. Lee, "Influence of Processing and Material Variables on Resin-Fiber Interface in Liquid Composite Molding", *Polymer Composites*, Vol. 14, No. 2, 161-172, 1993
10. Chan, A.W., and R.J. Morgan, "Modeling Preform Impregnation and Void Formation in Resin Transfer Molding of Unidirectional Composites", *SAMPE Quarterly*, 48, 1992
11. Chen, Y.T., H.T. Davis and C.W. Macosko, "Wetting of Fiber Mats for Composites Manufacturing: II. Air Entrapment Model", *AIChE J.*, 41, 2274, 1995
12. Mahale, A.D., R.K. Prud'homme, and L. Rebenfeld, "Quantitative Measurement of Voids Formed During Liquid Impregnation of Nonwoven Multifilament Glass Networks Using an Optical Visualization Technique", *Polymer Engineering and Science*, Vol. 32, No. 5, 319-326, 1992
13. Chen, Y.T., H.T. Davis and C.W. Macosko, "Wetting of Fiber Mats for Composites Manufacturing : I. Visualization Experiments", *AIChE Journal*, Vol. 41, No. 10, 2261-2273, 1995
14. Rohatgi, V., N. Patel and L.J. Lee, "Experimental Investigation of Flow Induced Microvoids During Impregnation of Unidirectional Stitched Fiberglass Mat", *Polymer Composites*, Vol. 17, No. 2, 1996